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Review

Liquid chromatography-high-resolution mass spectrometry for pesticide residue analysis in fruit and vegetables: Screening and quantitative studies

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ABSTRACT

This work reviews the current state-of-the-art of liquid chromatography coupled to high-resolution mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS) techniques applied to the analysis of pesticides in fruit-based and vegetable-based matrices. Nowadays, simultaneous trace analysis of hundreds of pesticides from different classes is required, preferably in just one run. The most commonly used QqQ-MS technology presents certain limitations in its application in a cost and effective way when analyzing a large number of pesticides. Thus, this review includes HRMS technology as a reliable complementary alternative allowing the analysis of a wide range of pesticides in food. Its capabilities and limitations in identifying, confirming and quantifying pesticides are discussed. HRMS instruments can adequately address such issues; however, the main drawbacks are as a result of insufficient prior optimization of the operational parameters during non-target analysis in full-scan mode and due to software shortcomings.

Keywords: Accurate mass; High resolution mass spectrometry; Pesticide; Screening TOF; Orbitrap

1. Introduction

Pesticide-residue analysis on fruit and vegetables is essential not only for the protection of human health but also to guarantee international trade and to comply with regulatory controls. More than 1000 substances that are active against pests are currently used worldwide [1]. Probably no other use of chemicals is regulated so extensively as it is for pesticides. The great number of possible residues means that it is necessary, where possible, to develop multiresidue methods (MRMs) in order to allow official laboratories to carry out effective control [2].

For pesticide testing in food, an extraction procedure as comprehensive as the MRM instrumental method is required. Nowadays, there are well-known general extraction procedures based on acetonitrile [3,4], ethyl acetate [5] or acetone [6], which are very effective for that purpose. A common practical analytical approach to MRMs applied in many routine laboratories which carry out pesticide-residue testing consists of selecting a list of around 100–200 compounds that are amenable to either gas (GC) and liquid chromatography (LC). Any significant increase to this number is uncommon for reasons of cost-effectiveness. Deciding which of these compounds has to be included in the analysis is not straightforward. This can only be done by using the established priority list combined with any other information related to agricultural uses in the region. Very important sources of information are the European Union (EU) reports from the European Food Safety Agency, in which a list of positive detections from official EU control programs has been collected. This means that the majority of low frequency, or misused compounds, are not targeted. Because of this, false negatives are guaranteed when residues from these lists are present in the sample. Consequently, it is desirable that the MRM approach implemented by official routine laboratories should be extended as far as possible to those pesticides commonly used in third countries, or even to misused compounds that might be available commercially on the “black market” [7]. It is fairly easy to find advertisements for a wide range of agrochemicals that are not approved (e.g. isofenphos methyl) or are no longer authorized in the EU, or in other countries, but nonetheless can be ordered via the Internet. From an analytical point of view, this task is hard to tackle as it involves extending the scope of the MRMs to several hundred chemicals.

MRMs are typically carried out using LC or GC coupled to triple quadrupole mass spectrometry (QqQ-MS) [4,8–11]. Over the last few years LC-MS/MS with electrospray (ESI) ionization has been gaining importance as a consequence of its

very high multiclass pesticide detection capability along with an increase in LC-amenable compounds new to the market compared to those amenable to GC. This technique provides very high sensitivity, selectivity and reproducibility operating in selective reaction monitoring mode – making LC-MS/MS a primary tool for pesticide residue analysis. Nonetheless, this approach results in a target analysis workflow where the set-up the acquisition method development is extensive and time-consuming for cases in which a few hundred pesticide residues are analyzed simultaneously in a single run. Furthermore, another drawback of this approach is its inability in detecting targeted compounds which have not been previously optimized; or in performing retrospective data analysis.

The use of high-resolution mass spectrometers (HRMS), such as TOF and Orbitrap, for multiresidue analysis benefits from the advantages of using the full-scan operation mode which can provide high specificity without limiting the number of simultaneously observed compounds. Therefore, method development is, in general, more flexible and more rapid than with LC-QqQ-MS. High resolving power, accurate mass measurement and high full-scan sensitivity makes HRMS an attractive tool for identifying both target and non-target compounds in complex food matrices.

Target analysis is based on searching for specific analytes, and involves establishing a method prior to analysis. Examples of applications for this kind of LC-TOF-MS analysis are the study of nicotine in mushrooms [12] or the analysis of 12 multiclass pesticides in fruit [13]. Isfenphos, isocarbophos and nitenpyram were also routinely analyzed in pepper after the sanitary alert in the autumn of 2006 [7]. Recently Orbitrap technology has been used for the study of chlorantraniliprole and cyantraniliprole in lettuce and orange [14]. One of the major advantages of HRMS instruments is their ability to record an unlimited number of compounds in full-scan mode. This characteristic allows the development of screening strategies based on accurate-mass databases for the identification of unexpected non-target pesticides, either because they are old products that are no longer authorized or, conversely, because they are very recent ones which are not yet integrated into current monitoring plans. These non-target pesticides may also be unexpected or not “controlled” by routine laboratories due to the different introduction and approval rates of new substances for agricultural practices by the respective authorities. Nevertheless, to be effective, the data evaluation of non-target methods should be carried out in an automated, rapid and simple way avoiding manual, time-consuming work. Several authors have reported the development and evaluation

of automated pesticide screening methods by LC-TOF-MS [15–20] and more recently using Orbitrap technology [21,22].

There are some reviews about the use of LC-HRMS instruments for the analysis of organic compounds in water and food matrices. Lacorte and Fenández-Alba [23] provided an overview of the applicability of LC-(Q)TOF-MS in determining the presence of target and non-target pesticides in environmental and food matrices. Botitsi et al. [24] discussed the most widely applied mass spectrometric (MS) approaches to pesticide and metabolite analysis including TOF, QTOF and Orbitrap mass spectrometers. More recently, Hernández et al. [25] provided a critical review about the use of HRMS instruments in environmental sciences, outlining the main characteristics of HRMS and its great potential in that field. Regarding different fields of food analysis, Kaufmann [26] discussed the role of HRMS instruments, including screening techniques and other aspects related to the potential, or limitations, in quantification and confirmation processes. This review presents the current state-of-the-art of HRMS analysis for pesticide residues in fruit and vegetable-based matrices and describes HRMS instrument capabilities for the identification, confirmation and quantification of pesticides.

2. Identification using HRMS instruments

Identification using HRMS instruments must be accomplished by the use of accurate mass and retention times. Accurate mass measurement provides the elemental composition of pesticides and allows a differentiation of isobaric compounds (different compounds with the same nominal mass but different elemental composition; and thus, different but nearly the same accurate mass). This feature allows for the possibility of increasing the confirmation capabilities of the instrument, given the greater information gathered when compared to lower resolution MS instruments. Consequently, the risk of reporting false positive findings is low, as accurate mass spectra provide much more accurate identification of target analytes in complex matrices such as certain fruit and vegetables.

The mass accuracies obtained for the most recent applications reported for analyzing pesticides in fruit and vegetable-based matrices using TOF and Orbitrap instruments are shown in Table 1. This table includes several studies of different matrices, concentration levels and different classes of pesticides, including metabolites or transformation products. In most cases, the mass accuracy in full-

scan mode, for different matrices and concentration levels, is lower than 5 ppm. Most pesticides and fragment ions show errors below this value, which is considered by several authors [15,17,20,22,27,28] to be an acceptable mass accuracy threshold for the confirmation of elemental composition. Nonetheless, pesticide mass errors are routinely even lower than 2-3 ppm. As an example, Gilbert et al. [29] reported a multiresidue method using LC-TOF-MS for the determination of 35 multi-class pesticides in fruit-based soft drinks. The accurate mass measurements of the protonated molecules and main fragments ions ranged between 0.4 and 4 ppm at a concentration level of 2 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; however, more than 90% of pesticide mass errors were below 2 ppm. The effect of different concentration levels and matrix complexity on the accuracy of mass measurements was evaluated by Ferrer et al. [30]. No significant differences were observed in the accuracy obtained from the various matrix-matched standards when compared to those prepared with pure solvents – with average values of around 1 ppm for all pesticides. Major deviations in accurate mass measurements (over 5 ppm) may be produced by the saturation of the detector caused by the high number of ions reaching it. Nevertheless mass accuracy could be affected by other parameters, some of them related, such as analyte concentration (very low and very high), matrix complexity and insufficient mass resolving power.

The use of isotopic patterns for identification purposes is another valuable indicator of the high degree of selectivity that can be obtained with HRMS instruments despite no real MS/MS experiments being performed [29]. The presence of high resolution isotopic clusters (i.e. due to Cl atoms) facilitates the identification of compounds containing these types of elements and provides evidence of the presence and the number of such atoms. These elemental compositions are then used as a search criterion in specific databases. There are several databases that can be used for the searching of pesticides. Commercial applications include the Merck Index (10,000 compounds total, 500 pesticides estimated) and ChemIndex (77,000 compounds total, 600 pesticides estimated) both from Cambridge Software [31]. These online databases provide comprehensive data on compounds. However, there are free accessible online databases, which are very useful for the search of unknown pesticides. As an example, the Sigma–Aldrich electronic catalog, the web-based data repository METLIN [32] which is specific for metabolites and the ChemSpider database [33], which provides structural search access to over 28 million structures from hundreds of data sources, properties and associated information.

The usefulness of the isotopic pattern for identification purposes is shown in Fig. 1. The figure shows a case of a false positive reported by LC-QqQ-MS and detected by LC-TOF-MS due to the lack of agreement with the chlorine isotopic pattern. A suspected peak initially identified as the chlorinated pesticide triflumuron ($C_{15}H_{10}ClF_3N_2O_3$) was detected by LC-QqQ-MS in leek extract. This compound fulfilled all the confirmation criteria required by the EU commission decision: the retention time and the peak area ratio of two selected MS/MS transitions. Nevertheless, the analyte spectra obtained using LC-TOF-MS did not show the characteristic isotopic profile of a chlorinated compound. Therefore, the suspected compound was an isobaric interference present in leek matrix with an elemental composition that did not include chlorine atoms.

2.1. Influence of co-extracted components

The complexity of certain matrices can cause problems with the ionization efficiency and in the detection systems of the analytical instruments. The number and distribution of interfering matrix components varies greatly depending on the particular vegetable matrix; even those included within the same commodity category according to EU guidelines [34]. As an example, in Table 2, the number of matrix compounds is shown for four different matrices (tomato, pepper, leek and orange) extracted by the QuEChERS method [3] and analyzed by LC-TOF-MS. The matrix compounds were retrieved and counted using the Molecular Feature Extractor (MFE) algorithm in the MassHunter Workstation Software. This software examines the entire chromatogram in order to search for and group all the ions that can be logically associated with a real chromatographic peak and may represent a “feature” of a molecule. Finally, the MFE creates a compound list of all the peaks in the data file that represent real molecules. Only compounds with an absolute height equal to, or greater than 10,000 counts were considered in this study. Table 2 also shows the number of components in a database of 300 pesticides, including the parent ion, Cl isotopes and fragment ions. The number of co-extracted matrix compounds is clearly higher in orange extract (8017 compounds), followed by leek (5870 compounds), pepper (3419 compounds) and tomato (2408 compounds). But the distribution of matrix compounds in the chromatogram is also a very important factor. The majority of the database components (750 components) eluted in the 7–13 min range. Therefore, although orange matrix presents many more compounds than leek extract, co-extracted

matrix compounds in orange are distributed in the first part of the chromatogram whilst they are more homogeneously distributed along all the chromatogram for leek. Consequently, in the time range of greatest interest, 7–13 min, the number of co-extracted compounds in orange (2743) is similar to the compounds extracted in leek (3032) yet well above the compounds present in pepper (919) and tomato (656). As a result, the quality of analysis is expected to be worse in leek and orange than in cleaner matrices like tomato and pepper: given that, among other things, the high amount of ions can saturate the detector and there is a high probability of overlap between the co-extracted compound and the target pesticides.

The presence of matrix compounds with similar masses to target analytes could be a major drawback for unequivocal pesticide identification and, as a consequence, the detection of false positives. Fig. 2 shows the number of isobaric interferences present in the four selected matrices compared to the masses in the 300 pesticide database. Mass differences were grouped in seven intervals: 0 to 1, to 0.1, to 0.04, to 0.02, to 0.01, to 0.005 and to 0.001 Da. The number of isobaric compounds is high in all studied matrices, but mainly in complex matrices such as leek and orange. In the mass difference range of 0 to 1 Da, more complex matrices (leek and orange) have over 9000 isobaric compounds and cleaner matrices (pepper and tomato), have over 3000 isobaric compounds. In the 0–0.02 Da range, the number of isobaric compounds is over 360 and 120 in complex and cleaner matrices, respectively. Due to the high amount of components sharing similar masses to target compounds, identification by HRMS instruments has to be accomplished using retention times. Most isobaric compounds are resolved by identifying retention times. Therefore, this tool provides a higher degree of specificity and is essential in minimizing the detection of false positives.

Another problem that may arise from the presence of isobaric compounds is the occurrence of false negatives. As mentioned before, many matrix compounds often have similar masses to target compounds, and in the case of co-elution of matrix compounds with analytes, the instrument might not be capable of fully resolving these two slightly different masses. Resolving power is an important factor in the correct identification of these compounds, especially in complex matrices. TOF instruments usually provide resolutions of up to 15,000 full width at half maximum (FWHM) and can even increase to more than 50,000 FWHM in new TOF instruments. Orbitrap (Exactive) technology currently provides resolutions of over 100,000 FWHM. In Fig. 3, the number of isobaric co-eluting interferences of matrix

compounds is shown with the masses included in the 300 pesticide database. Each matrix compound mass value was compared with all of the database masses in order to find mass differences in the range of 0–0.02 Da and 0–0.04 Da within a time frame of 0.5 min. These mass differences (0.02 and 0.04 Da), for an m/z of 300, signify a resolving power of 30,000 FWHM and 15,000 FWHM, respectively. Leek was the matrix with the highest number of interferences: with 75 matrix compounds in the range of 0–0.04 and 33 ions in the range of 0–0.02 Da – which could be resolved by instruments with a minimum resolving power of 30,000 FWHM. Despite pepper being a much cleaner matrix than orange (Table 2), they have similar isobaric interference values. In pepper, there are 35 compounds that have mass differences with target compounds between 0 and 0.04 Da and 26 compounds between 0 and 0.02 Da. The number of interferences in orange is 43 in the range of 0–0.04 Da and 24 (two less than in pepper) in the range of 0–0.02 Da. Tomato matrix does not present problems with isobaric interferences with only four interfering compounds in the two studied ranges.

2.2. Automatic screening: operational parameters

Automatic non-target methods have been revealed as a convenient tool for the large-scale screening of pesticides in foodstuffs [16]. However, important difficulties have to be overcome for their routine application and an in-depth study of the benefits and limitations has to be performed. Once a database has been established, software parameters for analyte detection need to be optimized in order to obtain a fit-for-purpose balance between false positives and false negatives reported by the software. Such parameters may include retention time tolerances, accurate mass tolerances, requirements for the presence of multiple adducts, isotope fits, fragment ions, ion ratios, and response thresholds [22].

Several authors have studied and optimized some of these search parameters. The parameters' values are strongly related to the analysis instruments and their characteristics. Mezcua et al. remarked on the importance of an adequate search parameter selection for the analysis of pesticides in fruit and vegetables. In this first study using a LC-TOF-MS system with a resolution power of 7500 FWHM, the peak filter (minimum number of chromatographic peak counts), retention time window and mass window were optimized. The peak filter threshold has to be low enough to find compounds in low concentrations and high enough to avoid false positives. For the instrument conditions, a value of 100 counts was selected as

a compromise for most of the studied samples. Different experiments were performed varying the retention time (RT) window tolerance between ± 0.05 min and ± 0.5 . The use of large RT windows might yield false positives, whereas a small RT window could give rise to false negatives. Typically, with the column and gradient selected in that study, the RT precision was very high (< 0.02 min for most of the compounds), but those eluting at the beginning of the gradient might be easily affected by the matrix as well as the column equilibration, and thus may vary slightly more. In order to avoid both false positives and negatives but, at the same time, missing the compounds present in the sample, the RT window was set at ± 0.15 min. The m/z tolerance is also a key parameter since it provides a high degree of procedure specificity and selectivity for unambiguous confirmation. Different mass windows were tested (± 50 mDa, ± 10 mDa, ± 1 mDa), combined with a ± 0.15 min RT window. Satisfactory results were obtained when combining an m/z tolerance of 1 mDa or 5 ppm with a ± 0.15 min RT window. The obtained rates for pesticide identification with the selected parameters at different concentration levels were over 95% [16]. Similar parameters were used by Polgár et al. [20] for the analysis of fruit and vegetable samples. In this study, real samples were analyzed by LC-TOF-MS and by LC-QqQ-MS in order to evaluate the relative coverage of the proposed screening method. Using the parameters mentioned above, 81% of pesticides were discovered with the automatic screening process. The false negatives obtained could be mostly explained by the higher sensitivity displayed by LC-QqQ-MS in multiple reaction monitoring mode.

In a second study by Mezcua et al. [17] using a different LC-QTOF-MS system, with higher sensitivity and resolution power (15,000 FWHM), the previous optimized parameters were not adequate and had to be adjusted. As an example, due to the enhanced sensitivity provided, false positives arose in some samples and therefore a higher value of peak filter had to be used (400 counts). Mass accuracy is affected by the mass resolution achieved and, for this reason a smaller mass tolerance was set at 0.6 mDa. Furthermore, the use of the same database in different systems involved a small variation in the pesticide retention time due to differences in the systems (such as dead volume) and, consequently, the RT window had to be increased to ± 0.3 min.

A similar example was documented by Malato et al. [15] using a LC-QTOF-MS working at 15,000 FWHM. The peak filter applied was set to 400 counts to avoid background or chemical noise. They concluded that changes in the mass tolerance set in the screening method considerably altered the automatic search results. In

order to avoid dependence on the compound mass search criteria, a relative mass error of 5 ppm was selected instead of an absolute value. The increase in the RT window (from ± 0.3 min to ± 0.5 min) can be useful in avoiding false negatives. Nevertheless, in the case of this study, it did not produce any changes in the automatic search results; instead it increased the number of false positives found, especially in complex matrices. Thus, the number of false positives in leek matrix was doubled from 3 to 7 in the worst case. Consequently, a time window of ± 0.3 min was considered to be the optimum.

False positives depend heavily on the matrix – the higher the complexity of the sample, the more false negatives and/or false positives will appear. Although false positives can be discarded after confirmation analysis by LC-MS/MS, they represent a time-consuming task and, therefore, an important handicap to efficient laboratory workflow. Due to this fact, software parameters must be configured in order to diminish false positive rates below 10% (or even better 5%).

Recently Mol et al. [22] optimized a screening method using LC coupled to a single-stage high resolution (Orbitrap) MS working at a resolving power of 50,000 FWHM (m/z 200). The study pointed out the use of response thresholds and diagnostic ions for the reduction of false positives. Due to the great variation in sensitivity between pesticides, a relative response threshold was set for each pesticide. This threshold was set at half the lowest response obtained for any of the studied matrices. With this value, the number of false positives was lowered from 88 to 14 without affecting the overall percentage of detected pesticides. The other parameters adjusted for the automatic screening were the mass tolerance (5 ppm), RT window (± 0.5 min) and the presence of two diagnostic ions (whether an adduct, an isotope or a fragment). Using the two-ion approach, the percentage of false positives was 0.3%. Furthermore, the percentage of false negatives was 13, 3 and 1% at the 0.01, 0.05 and 0.20 mg kg⁻¹ levels, respectively. Similar ratios were obtained by Hayward et al. [21]. In that study, an Orbitrap-MS (50,000 FWHM) successfully found 89% of 177 fortified pesticides in spinach matrix at 0.025 mg kg⁻¹.

One of the major limitations of non-target approaches is derived from possible unexpected matrix effects or a lack of MS parameter optimization which could lead to unexpected false negative results. It is possible to estimate the efficiency of the automatic screening method in identifying the selected compounds related to the tested matrix. As reported by Malato et al. [15], tomato and pepper extracts yielded the highest percentage of automatic positive findings (82–89%); in contrast to

“dirtier” matrices, such as orange and leek, which identified between 65 and 81%, in the studied concentration range. Zucchini was also found to be a complex matrix (81% on average). The number of unidentified compounds, regardless of the type of matrix, decreased with concentration. In leek, these were reduced from 24 (20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) to 12 (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$). In most cases, as can be seen in Fig. 4, for the pesticide demeton-s-methyl at a concentration level of 50 ng mL^{-1} , this is consequence of the signal suppression effect that reduces detectability at low concentrations.

A possible solution to this drawback in HRMS and MS/MS might be to perform extract dilution. Matrix effect occurs because of the interaction of co-eluting compounds with the analytes in the ionization process, producing, in some cases, signal suppression. As cited in Krueve et al. [35] this is believed to be largely due to competition between different compounds for the surface of the ESI droplets. A sample dilution decreases the number of these competing molecules per microdroplet, the ionization efficiency increases and, thus, the analyte signal increase. A dilution factor of 15 would be enough to solve most of the problems related to the presence of matrix components in the extracts [36], particularly problems of ionization efficiency and saturation of the detection system. The dilution effect on the number of co-extracted matrix components in leek extracts is clearly shown in Fig. 5. For this purpose, leek extracts with different dilution factors were analyzed using LC-TOF-MS and the m/z and retention times of all matrix components were collected. The x-axis represents the retention time and the y-axis represents the m/z for each compound. The graphic includes both the matrix compounds and the components of the 300 pesticide database. As stated above, most of the database components (750 components) were eluted in the 7–13 min range. Within this range, the number of co-eluting matrix compounds with database components decreases considerably with succeeding extract dilutions. Without any dilution at all, there are a large numbers of co-extracted compounds (3032) that would interfere in the pesticide analysis. With a dilution factor of 10, the number decreases to around 20% (2434) and with a dilution factor of 50, the number diminishes to 1410 interferences – similar values to those obtained in cleaner matrices such as pepper (Table 2). The main inconvenience of performing dilutions is in achieving sufficient sensitivity. Dilution of extracts implies a reduction in the analyte amount. Consequently, it is important to use very sensitive analytical systems which permit sub-ppb level detection.

In most cases, automatic screening methods are developed in positive ionization mode. However, in order to extend the scope of the screening methods,

it is necessary to perform analysis in both positive and negative ionization modes. This can be of great importance when monitoring pesticides such as ureas, neonicotinoids and triazoles. Very few databases contain negative ion species entries. Malato et al. [15] studied 97 pesticides – bromoxynil, terbacil, ioxynil, hexaflumuron, chlorfluazuron, orthophenylphenol and famoxadone could not be detected by ESI+, so they were analyzed in negative mode. Lacina et al. [19] applied a 212 pesticide database for the screening of different fruit and vegetables using UPLC-TOF-MS. Approximately 22% of those compounds were analyzed in negative mode. Diaz et al. [37] created a database separating positive and negative ionizable compounds for analysis using UPLC-TOF-MS in orange and banana. Here, Orbitrap has the advantage of providing coverage for all ESI-positive or-negative ion-amenable pesticides in a single screening, thus allowing broader coverage than using any other technique [21]. Consequently, Alder et al. [38] included negative species for the screening of pesticide residues in fruit and vegetables; whereas with Hayward et al. [21], 10% of pesticides were detected in negative mode in the same run.

Screening methods ought to be validated according to the SANCO guidelines “Method validation and quality control procedures for pesticide residue analysis in food and feed” [34]. Validation in cases of these kind of qualitative methods is focused on detectability. The guide defines the screening detection limit (SDL) of a qualitative screening method as the lowest concentration for which it has been demonstrated that a certain analyte can be detected (not necessarily meeting unequivocal identification criteria) in at least 95% of the samples (i.e. a false negative rate of 5% is accepted).

3. Confirmation by LC-MS/HRMS

HRMS systems provide screening and tentative identification for both non-target and target pesticides, whilst the MS/HRMS approach is required to confirm the identification of certain compounds, as in those that lack fragment ions, or present fragments with low intensity, or relative abundance, from in-source CID fragmentation. This enables the effective screening and tentative identification of a large number of species even without the need for standards as shown by [39]. Furthermore, as stated before, target and non-target screening strategies based on database searching are exposed to numerous false negatives and false positives that need to be clarified in the confirmatory step. This confirmation is also needed

for isomers which are not distinguished by full-scan mass spectra.

The potential of QTOF-MS/MS in assigning the structure of unknown species has been demonstrated by different authors. Most of the applications are dedicated to the analysis and elucidation of metabolites or pesticide degradation products. Analysis using UPLC-QTOF-MS/MS revealed the presence of amitraz degradation products in pears [40]. The same authors employed the same technique to confirm the structures of potential unknown compounds (imazalil, ethoxyquin, thiabendazole and diphenylamine) and their metabolites, previously determined using full-scan mode in pear [41] and/or to identify fenthion's degradation products in orange [42]. Carbosulfan and seven of its main metabolites were identified and confirmed in food matrices using LC-QTOF-MS/MS [43]; and UPLC-QTOF-MS/MS was applied to investigate the presence of pesticide metabolites of the parent pesticide in positive food samples [44]. In all of these cases, full scan mode was used for the structural elucidation of the compounds, and QTOF-MS/MS was applied for further identification.

In routine practice, the common strategy for targeted screening of a large number of pesticides, or non-targeted screening of unknowns, in a single analysis is to work in MS mode, then afterwards to perform a MS/MS analysis for confirmation of the detected compounds. In this second analysis, the retention time and precursor ion for each target compound are introduced into the method, and confirmation of their identity can be made by comparison of the structure of the proposed compound with the fragments obtained. This option is possible due to the fact that MS/MS mode provides abundant fragmentation compared to when the instrument is working in MS mode with only in-source fragment ions. Another possibility is the fragmentation of compounds without a previous precursor ion selection. This implies the fragmentation of all ions in the collision cell (QTOF), or in the HCD cell (Orbitrap). However, in that case, the fragmentation voltage cannot be applied selectively for each ion and this can make the proper fragmentation for some compounds difficult. For final confirmation, accurate mass data and isotopic distributions for the precursor and product ions can be compared to spectral data of reference compounds, if available, obtained under identical conditions.

For this purpose, libraries of MS/MS spectra can be very useful for rapid confirmation. The information contained in these libraries is the retention time, theoretically-calculated accurate mass data and accurate mass CID spectra of the pesticides. Mass spectral libraries are generally user-made, due to the difficulty in standardizing them according to the different operational conditions. The existence

in the market of different interfaces, ionization processes, voltages applied, mobile phase compositions etc., introduce diverse variables into the analytical measurement that make the development of standardized mass spectral libraries unfeasible. For this reason, building empirical in-house libraries containing as many compounds as possible is the best option at the moment, Fig. 6 shows the confirmation of the pesticide benalaxyl using a MS/MS spectra library with a score value above 85%. A comparison of the pesticide's MS/MS spectra in the sample (a) and the MS/MS spectra of the standard (b) leads to unequivocal identification (confirmation) of the compound. Currently, only a few MS/MS libraries have been developed, but most of them are in the environmental field. Diaz et al. [37] developed an empirical mass spectra library for the screening of organic contaminants, such as pesticides, in different samples. The spectra proved highly reproducible when the component was found at relatively high abundance, independent of the sample type analyzed. The confirmation of suspected compounds using the library was automatically performed and provided highly reliable identification.

One problem related to the MS/MS acquisition mode in QTOF instruments is that the accuracy of fragment ions might be worse than accuracies obtained in MS mode. Unlike errors normally obtained in MS mode, it is not difficult to find errors over 5 ppm in MS/MS mode [41,45,46]. This is mainly due to energy differences between ions coming from the second quadrupole. It is difficult to focus the kinetic energy of all the ions before each pulse in TOF and there are no calibration ions for continuous, on-line, accurate mass-measurement corrections. In this sense, the Orbitrap analyzer provides accurate masses for both protonated molecules and fragment ions [47].

In other cases, poor accuracy in the exact masses can be explained by low ion abundance, which increases the risk of interferences with co-eluting compounds of similar mass. Thus, depending on the interaction between the instrumental mass resolution, the mass difference and the relative abundance of the two signals, incorrect exact masses result from the insufficiently resolved spectrum [48]. Fig. 7 shows an example of a correct separation of two peaks due to the high resolving power of the mass spectrometer. Leek extract spiked with $0.1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of the pesticide imazalil was analyzed by an Exactive Orbitrap instrument working at a resolution of 70,000 FWHM (m/z 200). Due to imazalil's low concentration, the fragment ion signal is very low and the MS/MS spectrum of imazalil shows two similar peaks with a mass difference of 0.0038 Da. The first peak corresponds to a

fragment ion of imazalil and the other peak is matrix interference. In this case, resolution allows a separation of both peaks and the correct assignment of the fragment's mass with an error of 3.27 ppm.

4. Quantification by HRMS instruments

Historically, (Q)TOF instruments often suffered from narrow dynamic ranges, requiring mathematical algorithms, such as the "time to digital converter" (TDC), in order to attain a longer linear dynamic range. This severely limited the usability of these instruments for quantitative purposes, but the appearance of the "analog to digital converter" (ADC) improved the situation, providing an enhanced linear dynamic range, extended up to three orders of magnitude, and making possible its successful applicability to pesticide residue analyses. Even today, a common aspect of many (Q)TOF instruments is the saturation of the detector due to large peak intensities, which sometimes cause the calibration curves to be linear only at the lowest concentration levels. As an example, the pesticide ethoxyquin causes detector saturation at 100 µg/kg, while detector saturation already occurs at 50 µg/kg for more sensitive compounds such as propazine and terbutylazine [15].

Another limitation that has prevented (Q)TOF analyzers from being as efficient in pesticide residue control as other methods is the need for low detection limits (e.g., 0.01 mg kg⁻¹). Nevertheless, over the last decade a new generation of (Q)TOF instruments has gained considerable acceptance by offering high sensitivity and selectivity under full-scan conditions, higher resolutions, and especially high mass accuracies. On the other hand, Orbitrap instruments allow resolutions at over 100,000 FWHM as well as greater sensitivity as a result of, among other things, their capability to resolve analytes from isobaric matrix-related interferences, resulting in superior S/N [49].

Several authors have compared the quantitative capabilities of HRMS instruments to MS/MS systems. Such studies are valuable indicators of the potential of LC-TOF-MS for large-scale quantitative multiresidue analysis. Taylor et al. [50] evaluated the potential of UPLC-TOF-MS for the quantitative analysis of 100 pesticides in strawberry. The method was assessed by comparing results with those obtained using a UPLC-MS/MS MRM. The calibration, using matrix-matched standards, was performed over the 0.005–0.04 mg kg⁻¹ concentration range and pesticide linearity was demonstrated in the studied range ($r^2 > 0.99$) with the exception of

malathion, fenarimol, fludioxanil, quassia, pymetrazine, and fenthion sulfone ($r^2 < 0.98$). Residues found in the samples ranged from 0.025 to 0.28 mg kg⁻¹ and they were in excellent agreement with results obtained using UPLC-MS/MS. In a recent study [17], a semi-quantification of fruit and vegetable samples was performed in solvent-matched solutions at two concentration levels (10 and 100 µg/kg). The results were compared with those obtained by LC-MS/MS. The summarized results obtained were 97 pesticides found at a concentration lower than 10 µg/kg, 53 pesticides in a concentration range between 10 and 100 µg/kg, and 60 pesticides at a concentration higher than 100 µg/kg. Most of the concentrations given by LC-TOF-MS were lower than those given by LC-MS/MS, but these differences were either lower or very close to 50%, an accepted value of uncertainty in the DG SANCO guidelines [34]. Nevertheless, some pesticides identified by LC-MS/MS were not found by applying LC-TOF-MS (21 pesticides) because their LOD values were higher than the LODs of the LC-QqQ-MS method used for confirmation purposes. Lacina et al. [19] investigated the potential of UPLC-TOF-MS in the analysis of 212 pesticides in apple, strawberry, spinach and tomato. The obtained quantification limits (LOQs) were 10 µg/kg and lower for 96% of the pesticides under study. Compared with tandem mass analyzers such as triple quadrupole the sensitivity of TOF is lower and the linear dynamic range of the studied instrument is rather narrower. However, the authors stated that LC-TOF-MS is a challenging complementary alternative to current pesticide analysis by LC-MS/MS based strategies. Only a limited number of articles have evaluated the use of LC-QTOF working in MS/MS mode for quantification of pesticides in food matrices. Pico et al. [40] validated a method using LC-QTOF-MS and LC-QTOF-MS/MS for the quantification of amitraz in pear. Using QTOF-MS/MS – the recoveries, the linearity and the precision were similar to those obtained in full-scan mode, but LOQs were higher because of the intense fragmentation of the protonated molecules in the product mass spectrum. Grimalt et al. [46] explored the potential of LC-QTOF-MS/MS mode for quantification of buprofezin and hexythiazox in orange, banana, strawberry and pear. The results showed that QTOF can be used for quantification purposes with a suitable linearity range of more than 2 orders of magnitude along with satisfactory sensitivity – comparable to that obtained in full-scan TOF analyzers, although still lower than that for QqQ instruments. In a more recent study by Grimalt et al. [39], the potential of QqQ, TOF and QTOF was investigated and compared for the quantification of eleven pesticides in nine fruit and vegetable matrices. In general, QqQ presented a wider linear range and higher sensitivity than TOF – working in

full-scan mode and QTOF working in MS/MS mode. For all instruments and matrices studied, LOQs around 0.01 mg kg^{-1} were reached. However, in this study, the selection of different precursor ions in QTOF negatively affected the chromatographic peak shape due to the decrease in the data point rate, which can affect accurate quantitation. Because of this, and based on our experience, when a high number of pesticides are analyzed, the use of LC-QTOF-MS/MS selecting the precursor ion in the acquisition method cannot guarantee adequate quantitation in all cases. When three or more precursor ions are concurrent in a retention time range of 0.5 min, the cycle time increases and, because of this, fewer spectra for each compound are obtained. This translates into chromatographic peaks with an inadequate number of points for an accurate quantitation.

Until now, there are very few published studies regarding the use of Orbitrap instruments for the quantitation of pesticides in fruit and vegetables. Recently, Kaufmann et al. [49] evaluated the capability of current Orbitrap technology to substitute LC-MS/MS technology for the analysis of 240 analytes in lettuce, pepper and rocket. With regard to the dynamic range ($1\text{--}100 \text{ }\mu\text{g/kg}$), both techniques showed comparable capabilities. Similar performance regarding precision, accuracy, sensitivity and selectivity was observed for both technologies but HRMS sensitivity was found to be slightly inferior to MS/MS methods as it was dedicated to less than 300 monitored compounds. However as stated by the authors, this is only a limitation for a few analytes that have to be detected at very low concentration in certain matrices. The major disadvantage of HRMS technology found in this study was the data processing speed, which took significantly longer than for LC-MS/MS data due to the limited capabilities of the software. In another study using the Orbitrap technology, Kellmann et al. [51] evaluated the effect of the resolving power for quantitation of different organic compounds in honey and animal feed. The results showed that, for an accurate quantitation at low analyte levels in complex matrices, a resolving power of 50,000 FWHM (m/z 200) or higher is required. This is necessary in order to avoid peak distortion when using mass extraction windows, needed for appropriate selectivity. In the case of the less complex honey matrix, a resolving power of 25,000 FWHM was adequate for analyte quantitation at levels of 10 ng g^{-1} . The authors also determined the deviation between theoretical and calculated concentration for 14 analytes in a concentration range between 10 and 250 ng g^{-1} . This deviation was generally less than 20% except for the lowest concentration level.

5. Conclusions

Currently, QqQ-MS is the first-line choice for routine pesticide residue analysis. Such systems allow target residue identification and quantification with an adequate concentration range and reproducibility in complex food matrices at extremely low levels (ng kg^{-1}). Nevertheless, they present limitations for its application in a cost and effective way when a high number of compounds (several hundred) are analyzed in a single run. On the other hand, HRMS systems provide high resolution, accurate mass and high full-scan sensitivity and selectivity, making them attractive for residue analysis in food. They allow operation for both target and non-target compounds (recording an unlimited number of compounds), and permitting one to work in full-scan mode or MS/MS mode, and in sequential or simultaneous mode. This translates into a rapid, effective option for routine laboratories. Other advantages of these instruments are the possibility for *a posteriori* analysis and their usefulness in identifying unknown compounds. The use of HRMS instruments in food analysis laboratories has been limited, until now, by certain drawbacks belonging to the previous generation of analytical systems. These were (i) accurate mass data obtained above 5 ppm; (ii) lower resolving powers than 20000; (iii) saturation effects with certain compounds; (iv) short, and compound-dependent, dynamic range; and (v) the presence of false positives working in a full-scan mode with databases containing only the (de)protonated molecules. Practically all these problems have now been solved with improvements to the update systems and by combining full-scan and MS/MS modes. Nevertheless, there are still some issues – mainly caused by the lack of preliminary optimization parameters for each compound in full-scan mode. Thus, depending on the pesticide and matrix being analyzed, detection problems (false negatives) may occur. This can be solved, to a great extent by using very sensitive instruments so the matrix effect can be minimized performing extract dilution. Another problem comes from the software which needs to be enhanced for a better fit-for-purpose performance in non-target analysis and for an increase in data processing speed in quantitation processes. To overcome this drawback, an effort by instrument companies to provide upgraded software is necessary.

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Glossary

Identification: qualitative result from a method capable of providing structural information that meets acceptable criteria for the purpose of the analysis

Tentative identification: identification where a reasonable doubt about the correctness exists

Confirmation: combination of two or more analyses that are in agreement with each other (ideally, using methods of orthogonal selectivity) when at least one of which meets identification criteria

(Q)TOF: time-of-flight or quadrupole time-of-flight

CID: collision-induced-dissociation

ESI: electrospray ionization

EU: European Union

FWHM: full width at half maximum

GC: gas chromatography

HCD: higher energy collisional dissociation *HRMS*: high-resolution-mass spectrometry *LC*: liquid chromatography

LCL: lowest calibrated level

LC-MS/MS: liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry

LC-QqQ-MS: liquid chromatography coupled to triple quadrupole mass spectrometry

LC-QTOF-MS: liquid chromatography coupled to quadrupole time-of-flight mass spectrometry

LC-TOF-MS: liquid chromatography coupled to time-of-flight mass spectrometry

LOD: limit of detection *LOQ*: limit of quantitation *m/z*: mass-to-charge ratio

MFE: molecular feature extraction

MRMs: multiresidue methods

MS: mass spectrometry

MS/HRMS: high-resolution tandem mass spectrometry

MS/MS: tandem mass spectrometry

QqQ: triple quadrupole

QTOF: quadrupole time-of-flight

QuEChERS: Quick, Easy, Cheap, Effective, Rugged, Safe, extraction method

SDL: screening detection limit

S/N: Signal to noise-ratio

TOF: time-of-flight

UPLC: ultra performance liquid chromatography

UPLC-QTOF-MS: ultra performance liquid chromatography coupled to quadrupole time-of-flight mass spectrometry

UPLC-TOF-MS: ultra performance liquid chromatography coupled to time-of-flight mass spectrometry

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Fig. 1. (a) False positive of triflumuron detected in leek using LC-QqQ-MS/MS. MS/MS selected transitions (ratio 0.6). (b) LC-TOF-MS extracted ion chromatogram of the suspected compound with m/z 359. (c) LC-TOF-MS spectrum of the suspected compound without the characteristic isotopic profile of a chlorinated compound (boxed).

Fig. 2. Ranges of exact mass differences between the ions in the pesticide database and ions of matrix compounds.

Fig. 3. Pesticides and interferences with exact mass differences from 0 to 0.02 Da and from 0 to 0.04 Da, with retention time differences lower than 0.5 min.

Fig. 4. LC-TOF-MS extracted ion chromatograms using a mass extraction window of ± 20 ppm, of demeton-s-methyl (m/z 253.0092) at a concentration level of 50 ng mL^{-1} in tomato, leek, orange, pepper and zucchini matrices.

Fig. 5. Components of a pesticide database (300 pesticides) and co-eluting matrix compounds of leek extracts analyzed using LC-TOF-MS (absolute height 10,000 counts). The x-axis represents the retention time and the y-axis the m/z . The top graphic includes matrix compounds of leek extract without dilution and the lower includes compounds of leek extract with a dilution factor of 50.

Fig. 6. Confirmation of benalaxyl using a MS/MS spectra library with a score above 85. (a) Acquired spectrum. (b) Library spectrum.

Fig. 7. Leek extract spiked with imazalil at 0.1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ analyzed using Orbitrap working at 70,000 FWHM. (a) MS extracted ion chromatogram of imazalil. (b) MS/MS extracted ion chromatogram of imazalil. (c) MS/MS fragment of imazalil (m/z 255) and properly separated matrix interference.

Table 1. Overview of LC-(Q)TOF-MS(/MS) and Orbitrap applications for the analysis of pesticides in fruits and vegetables.

Matrix	Compounds	Preparation method	Analytical method			Sensitivity	Accuracy MS ^b	References
			Detection mode	Resolution ^a (FWHM)	LC column			
Orange peel and flesh, banana peel and flesh, strawberry, tomato, grapefruit, cucumber and pepper	Azoxystrobin, buprofezin, chlorpyrifos, diflufenzuron, hexythiazox, imazalil, imidachlorprid, pyriproxyfen, tebufenozide, thiabendazole and spinosad	Solvent extraction Methanol:water (80:20)	UPLC-TOF-MS UPLC-QTOF-MS/MS ESI (+)	10,000	C18 50 mm × 2.1 mm, 1.7 μm 0.5 mM NH ₄ OAc in methanol/0.5 mM NH ₄ OAc in water	LOQ range: 2–125 μg/kg	0.3–2.6 mDa	[39]
Pear	Amitraz and transformation products	Solvent extraction Ethyl acetate	UPLC-QTOF-MS UPLC-QTOF-MS/MS ESI (+)	5000	C18 50 mm × 2.1 mm, 1.7 μm Methanol/ammonium formate (10 mM) in water	LOQ range: 0.005–0.030 mg kg ⁻¹	n.a	[40]
Orange peel and flesh, banana skin and flesh, strawberry and pear	Non target (Buprofezin and hexythiazox)	Solvent extraction Acetone	LC-QTOF-MS LC-QTOF-MS/MS ESI (+)	5000	C18 50 mm × 2.1 mm, 5 μm C18 250 mm × 2.1 mm, 5 μm 0.01% Formic acid in methanol/0.01% formic acid in water	LCL range: 0.01–0.075 mg kg ⁻¹	0–3.3 mDa	[46]
Orange, tomato, leek	53 pesticides	QuEChERS Acetonitrile	LC-QTOF-MS ESI (+)	15,000	C8 150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm Acetonitrile/0.1% formic acid in water	n.a.	n.a.	[36]
Tomato, pepper, zucchini, orange and leek	97 pesticides	QuEChERS Acetonitrile	LC-QTOF-MS ESI (+) and ESI (–)	15,000	C18 50 mm × 4.6 mm, 1.8 μm Positive mode: 0.1% formic acid and 5% water in acetonitrile/0.1% formic acid in water (pH 3.5) Negative mode: 5% water in acetonitrile/5% acetonitrile in water	n.a.	<5 ppm	[15]
Pepper, broccoli, tomato, orange, lemon, apple and melon	15 pesticides	Solvent extraction Ethyl acetate	LC-TOF-MS ESI (+)	7500	C8 150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm Acetonitrile/0.1% formic acid in water	LOD range: 0.3–50 μg/kg	0.03–1.81 ppm	[30]
Pepper	Nitenpyram, isocarbophos and isofenphos-methyl	QuEChERS Acetonitrile	LC-TOF-MS ESI (+)	7500	C8 150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm Acetonitrile/0.1% formic acid in water	LOD range: 0.06–0.6 μg/kg	0.3–1.8 ppm	[7]
Fruits and vegetables	297 pesticides-database	QuEChERS Acetonitrile	LC-TOF-MS ESI (+)	7500	C18 50 mm × 4.6 mm, 1.8 μm 0.1% formic acid and 5% water in acetonitrile/0.1% formic acid and 5% acetonitrile in water	n.a.	0.1–1.8 ppm	[16]
Fruit-based soft drinks	33 Multiclass pesticides	SPE (Oasis HLB) Methanol	LC-TOF-MS ESI (+)	7500	C18 50 mm × 4.6 mm, 1.8 μm Acetonitrile/0.1% formic acid in water	LOQ range: 0.02–2 μg/kg	0.4–4 ppm	[29]

Apple and orange	350 pesticides-database	Solvent extraction Ethyl acetate	LC-TOF-MS ESI (+)	7500	C8 150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm Acetonitrile/0.1% formic acid in water	n.a.	0–6 ppm	[18]
Mushrooms	Nicotine	QuEChERS Acetonitrile	LC-TOF-MS ESI (+)	7500	C18 3 mm × 250 mm, 5 µm 0.1% formic acid in acetonitrile/0.1% formic acid in water	LOQ: 10 µg/kg	n.a.	[12]
Fruits and vegetables	300 pesticides-database	QuEChERS Acetonitrile	LC-TOF-MS LC-QTOF-MS ESI (+)	7500 15000	C18 50 mm × 4.6 mm, 1.8 µm 0.1% formic acid and 5% water in acetonitrile/0.1% formic acid and 5% acetonitrile in water	n.a.	<5 ppm	[17]
Apple, pepper, broccoli, cucumber, tomato, grapefruit, orange, lemon, pear, carrot, eggplant, lettuce, grapes, pineapple, strawberry and melon	Chlorinated pesticides	QuEChERS Acetonitrile	LC-TOF-MS ESI (+)	7500	C8 150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm Acetonitrile/0.1% formic acid in water	n.a.	0.08–3.2 ppm	[28]
Strawberries	100 pesticides	Solvent extraction Ethyl acetate	UPLC-TOF-MS ESI (+) and ESI (-)	11,500	C18 50 mm × 2.1 mm, 1.7 µm Ammonium acetate (5 mM) in methanol/Ammonium acetate (10 mM) in water/methanol 95:5 v/v	LCLrange: 10–20 µg/kg	0–5.1 ppm	[50]
Orange, pear, peach, apricot, strawberries and cherries	12 pesticides (acrinathrin, bupirimate, buprofezin, cyproconazole, λ-cyhalothrin, fluvalinate, hexaflumuron, kresoxim-methyl, propanil, pyrifenoxy, pyriproxyfen and tebufenpyrad)	Solvent extraction Ethyl acetate PLE (acidic alumina) Ethyl acetate	LC-TOF-MS ESI (+)	n.a.	C18 150 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 µm Ammonium formate (10 mM) in methanol/ammonium formate (10 mM) in water	LOQ range: 0.01–0.4 mg kg ⁻¹	1.9–4.1 ppm	[13]
Apple and pear	Ethoxyquin, imazalil, diphenylamine,	Solvent extraction Ethyl acetate	UPLC-QTOF-MS UPLC-QTOF-MS/MS ESI (+)	5000	C18 150 mm × 2.1 mm, 1.7 µm Ammonium formate (10 mM) in methanol/Ammonium formate (10 mM) in water	LOQ range: 0.05–1 µg on the fruit	0–6 ppm	[41]
Apple, strawberries, tomato and	thiabendazole and their degradations products. 212 pesticides	QuEChERS Acetonitrile	UPLC-TOF-MS ESI (+) and ESI (-)	11,000	C18 100 mm × 2.1 mm, 1.8 µm Methanol/Ammonium	LOQ range: <10 µg/kg	n.a.	[19]

spinach					formate			
Orange, potato, and rice	Carbosulfan and seven of its main metabolites	PLE (anhydrous sodium sulfate)	LC-QTOF-MS LC-QTOF-MS/MS	n.a.	C14 150 mm × 2.1 mm, 5 μm	LOQ range: 10–70 μg/kg	n.a	[43]
	(carbofuran, 3-hydroxycarbofuran, 3-ketocarbofuran, 3-hydroxy- 7-phenol carbofuran, 3-keto-7-phenolcarbofuran, 7-phenolcarbofuran, dibutylamine)	Dichloromethane	ESI (+)		in acetonitrile/Ammonium acetate (1.0 mM) in methanol/Ammonium acetate (1.0 mM) in water			
Orange	Fenthion and its metabolites	Solvent extraction Ethyl acetate	UPLC-QTOF-MS UPLC-QTOF-MS/MS	5000	C18 50 mm × 2.1 mm, 1.7 μm	LOQ range: 4–15 μg/kg	0–2.9 ppm	[42]
Lemon, grapes	Imazalil, chlorpyrifos and their metabolites	Solvent extraction	ESI (+) UPLC-QTOF-MS	10,000	C18 100 mm × 2.1 mm, 1.7 μm	n.a	0.2–2.3 mDa	[44]
Olive oil	Phosmet and its metabolites	Methanol/water (80:20, v/v)	UPLC-QTOF-MS/MS		Ammonium acetate (0.5 mM)			
		LLE Acetonitrile/Hexane	ESI (+) and ESI (–)		in methanol/Ammonium acetate (0.5 mM) in water			
Orange, banana	Multi-class pesticides	Solvent extraction Methanol/water (80:20, v/v)	UPLC-QTOF-MS UPLC-QTOF-MS/MS ESI (+) and ESI (–)	10,000	C18 150 mm × 2.1 mm, 1.7 μm	n.a.	<2 mDa	[37]
					0.01% formic acid in methanol/0.01% formic acid in water			
Fruits and vegetables	850 pesticides-database	QuEChERS Acetonitrile	LC-TOF-MS ESI (+)	n.a.	C18 50 mm × 4.6 mm, 1.8 μm	n.a.	0–3.46 ppm	[20]
Cucumber, lemon	500 pesticides-database	QuEChERS Acetonitrile	LC-Orbitrap-MS ESI (+) and ESI (–)	100,000	C18 50 mm × 2 mm, 5 μm	LOD range: 1–100 μg/kg	<5 ppm	[38]
Spinach	189 pesticides-database	QuEChERS Acetonitrile	UPLC-Orbitrap-MS ESI (+) and ESI (–)	50,000	T3 100 mm × 2.1 mm, 1.8 μm	LOD: 25 μg/kg	n.a	[21]
					Ammonium formate (4 mM/L) 0.1% formic acid in methanol/Ammonium formate (4 mM/L)0.1% formic acid in water			
Fruits and vegetables	556 pesticides-database	QuEChERS Acetonitrile 0.1% acetic acid	LC-Orbitrap-MS ESI (+)	50,000	T3 100 mm × 3 mm, 1.8 μm	LOD range: 10–200 μg/kg	<5 ppm	[22]
					Ammonium formate (2 mM/L) 0.002% formic acid in methanol/Ammonium formate (2 mM/L)0.002% formic acid in water			
Lettuce and orange	Chlorantraniliprole and	QuEChERS	LC-Orbitrap-MS	100,000	C18 50 mm × 2 mm, 5 μm	LOQ 10 μg/kg	n.a	[14]

	cyantraniliprole	<i>Acetonitrile</i>	ESI (+)			Ammonium formate (5 mM/L) 0.1% formic acid in methanol/Ammonium formate (5 mM/L) 0.1% formic acid in water			
Lettuce, hot pepper and rocket	240 pesticides	Solvent extraction Ethyl acetate 1% acetic acid	LC-Orbitrap-MS ESI (+)	50,000		C18 100 mm × 2.1 mm, 1.8 μm 0.01% formic acid in methanol/0.01% formic acid 2% methanol in water	LOQ 0.5–100 μg/kg	n.a	[49]

n.a., information non available.

^a Resolution estimated at m/z ranges between 200 and 550.

^b Considering different matrix and concentration levels.

Table 2. Number co-extracted compounds (absolute height $\geq 10,000$ counts) of each matrix along all chromatogram time and in a selected retention time range. Samples were extracted with QuEChERS method and analyzed by LC-TOF-MS.

Matrix	No of co-extracted compounds	
	Rt: 0–17 min	Rt: 7–13 min
Orange	8017	2743
Leek	5870	3032
Pepper	3419	919
Tomato	2408	656
300 Pesticide-database components	912	750